

A STUDY OF B.ED. PASS-OUT STUDENT'S OPINION ABOUT CURRICULUM**Dr.Prashant Kale**

Associate Professor,

GE Society's College of Education,Parel, Mumbai

Introduction:

Teachers are the nation builders. Quality of school education is depended on the quality of teachers. In the recent past there are tremendous changes in the field of teacher education. From the year 2015 B.Ed. course is changed to one year to two years. It was a revolutionary change. Improvement in the quality of teachers is the main objective behind this change. All the universities across the country have accepted this change and they are implementing two-year B.Ed. course.

Importance of the Study:

A curriculum is a tool to implement a course. Curriculum formation, continuous feedback, evaluation of curriculum and revision of curriculum are the important steps regarding curriculum. In the year 2015 when two-year B.Ed. is all the universities in India revised the B.Ed. curriculum as per the guidelines given by NCTE. Two-year B.Ed. has now completed five years are, it is a time to study the pass out students' opinion about curriculum. The present study is a small effort in this direction to understand the views of B.Ed. pass-out students about curriculum they studied. With the help of this study educationists will get insight for curriculum modification and revision of curriculum.

Objectives of the study:

For the present study the researcher had formulated following objectives.

- 1) to study the opinion of B.Ed. pass-out students about curriculum.
- 2) to suggest the modifications in the curriculum on the basis of facts revealed from the study.

Methodology and Sample of the study:

For the present study the researcher has selected a Survey method. The data is collected with the questionnaire. The researcher personally distributed the questionnaire and collected the data. For the present study for the present study students who have completed their B.Ed. in 2017, 2018,2019 are considered. The researcher has received responses from 132 students.

Tool of the data Collection:

The researcher has prepared a questionnaire and personally distributed and collected the data. There were 21 items constructed which are related to the curriculum of B.Ed. they studied. In the 21 items in the questionnaire there was a freedom given to the teachers that if they do not want to attempt particular question, they were free to do so. Students passed B.Ed. from University of Mumbai and SNTD Women's University were considered.

Statistical Techniques used:

For the analysis of the data simple statistical tool i.e., percentage is used.

Analysis of the Data:

On the basis of responses received following facts are revealed.

- 1) The researcher has received 132 responses from the B.Ed. pass-out students. Year wise distribution is as follows.

2017	46
2018	29
2019	57
Total	132

2) As far as methods of B.Ed. was considered the distribution is as follows.

Marathi	9.1%
Hindi	18.2%
English	28%
Science	26.5%
Maths	24.2%
History	18.9%
Geography	9.8%
Economics	9.8%
Commerce	12.9%

- 3) Among the 132 respondents 70.2% students are working as a school or college teacher.
- 4) Among the respondents 78.1% students are working in unaided school/college and 21.9% students are working in aided school/college.
- 5) 78.6% B.Ed. pass-out students are working in unaided English medium schools. 17.3% students are working in Hindi medium schools, some students are working in Marathi, Gujrati and Urdu medium schools.
- 6) 17.3% B.Ed. pass-out students have accepted profession other than teaching profession.
- 7) 32.5% students are engaged with private tuitions.
- 8) 87.7% students expressed that they are happy with teaching profession.
- 9) 57.7% students are pursuing higher studies after B.Ed. 42.3% students are not pursuing any course or higher education after B.Ed.
- 10) From these 57% are taking higher education in distance mode .43% students are taking in regular mode.
- 11) 84.5% students expressed that B.Ed. curriculum proved very helpful for them to perform duties of teacher effectively.
- 12) 91.6% students expressed that whatever they have learnt in B.Ed. that they are implementing for teaching.
- 13) All the respondents expressed that all the activities in B.Ed. curriculum were very interesting and they learnt many new things. Activities like internship, technology-based lessons, practice lessons, co-curricular activities, understanding -self activity, drama art and education proved very beneficial for them to perform duties as a teacher.
- 14) Students learnt new methodologies like Constructivist approach, co-operative learning strategies, educational thinkers, use of ICT, peer-evaluation, activity-based learning, team teaching.
- 15) 59.9% students expressed that there is a scope for adding more activities and improvement in B.Ed. curriculum. 40.6% students are satisfied with present curriculum.
- 16) Students expressed that hands on experience of technology should be given. Students also expressed that number of practice lessons should be increased; more new methods of teaching should be included in B.Ed. curriculum. B.Ed. curriculum should help students to become global teachers. There should be workshops for English communication, e-tutors, experiential learning. While completing B.Ed. itself

there should be preparation of TET and CTET examination. Industry and education collaboration is also needed in the curriculum.

- 17) 83.8% students agreed that B.Ed. course is very helpful and sufficient for becoming a good teacher.
- 18) 70.5% students agreed that the duration of B.Ed. should be two years where as 26.4% students are in favour of one year B.Ed.
- 19) 46.5% students desired to take admission for M.Ed. in future.
- 20) 91% students expressed that completing B.Ed. was a memorable and very nice experience.
- 21) 80.2% students said that they will certainly refer their graduate friends to complete B.Ed. course.

Recommendations on the basis of above findings:

On the basis of above findings following recommendations can be given.

- 1) Teacher training colleges should give more hands-on practice regarding ICT.
- 2) Guidance of Teacher Eligibility Tests should be included in B.Ed. curriculum.
- 3) Components like e-tutor, virtual learning should be given more focus to help B.Ed. students to become global teachers.
- 4) Components of practice teaching and internship should be given more importance.
- 5) Teacher training colleges should introduce short courses for effective communication.

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